

Studies on Indigoid Dyes: Part IX. Benzylidene-2-Iodothionaphthenes

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Twelve new iodothioindogenides have been prepared by condensing 6-iodothioindoxyl and 7-iodothioindoxyl respectively with benzaldehyde, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes, *p*-dimethylamino and *p*-diethylamino-benzaldehydes and two more dyes by condensing 5-iodothioindoxyl with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde. Results of previous communication have been collated and it has been shown that with regard to the absorption maxima, substitution of iodine atom at the 5-position of the thioindoxyl is more effective than at the 6- and 7-positions.

The preparation and properties of some 5-iodothioindogenides were reported earlier¹.

The present investigation is in continuation of the work undertaken with the object of studying the effect of an iodine atom when present in 5-, 6-, and 7-position respectively of the thionaphthene nucleus of benzylidenethionaphthenes.

The effect on absorption due to the introduction of different substituents such as nitro (in *o*-, *m*-, *p*-positions), *p*-dimethylamino-, and *p*-diethylamino- in the benzaldehyde part of the benzylidenethionaphthenes has also been studied.

The dyes (M_1 , M_2) have been prepared by condensing 5-iodothioindoxyl with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde.

6-Iodothioindoxyl has been condensed successively with benzaldehyde, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes, *p*-dimethylamino and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehydes affording the dyes (G_1 , G_2 , G_3 , G_4 , G_5 , G_6) respectively.

A similar series of 7-iodothioindogenides (L_1 , L_2 , L_3 , L_4 , L_5 , L_6) have been prepared by condensing 7-iodothioindoxyl with the above mentioned aldehydes.

These compounds have the general formula (M, G and L):

M_1 : 2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 M_2 : 3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene

- G₁: Benzylidene-2-(6-iodo) 3-oxy 2, 3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 G₂: 2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 G₃: 3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 G₄: 4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 G₅: 4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo) 3-oxy 2, 3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 G₆: 4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene

- L₁: Benzylidene-2-(7-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 L₂: 2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 L₃: 3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 L₄: 4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene
 L₅: 4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro: thionaphthene
 L₆: 4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo) 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro: thionaphthene

All these iodothioindogenides possess yellow colour but the *p*-dialkylamino compounds have a red colour. They dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid producing characteristic colourations. The iodothioindogenides develop lighter shade on cotton on reduction by alkaline hydrosulphite and subsequent aerial oxidation. The compounds are not completely reducible by alkaline hydrosulphite and hence a light shade is produced. The properties of the compounds are given in table II.

The order of reduction is in agreement with 5-iodothioindogenides¹ reported earlier.

The light absorption measurements of these dyes in the visible region were determined in pyridine solution using a Hilger and Watts' spectrophotometer and are reported in table I.

A scrutiny of the absorption figures reveals that the 5-iodothioindogenides absorbs at a longer wavelength than the corresponding 7-iodo- and 6-iodothioindogenides and they are in the order:

TABLE I

T = 3-oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene

Compound	λ_{Py} max. in $m\mu$	log ϵ	Ref. No.
Benzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	448	4.169	I
Benzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	437	4.139	
Benzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	436	4.114	
2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	447	3.913	I
2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	434	3.876	
2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	432	4.040	
3''-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	449	3.979	I
3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	438	4.006	
3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	437	3.903	
4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	462	3.798	I
4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	450	4.115	
4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	449	4.191	
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	506	4.585	I
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	498	4.677	
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	495	4.611	
4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	514	3.866	I
4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	507	4.666	
4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	506	4.532	

The value of molar extinction co-efficients in the different series are in the following order:

5-iodo series: $(CH_3)_2N > \text{unsubstituted} > m\text{-NO}_2 > o\text{-NO}_2 > (C_2H_5)_2N > p\text{-NO}_2$

6-iodo series: $(CH_3)_2N > (C_2H_5)_2N > p\text{-NO}_2 > \text{unsubstituted} > o\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2$

7-iodo series: $(CH_3)_2N > (C_2H_5)_2N > \text{unsubstituted} > p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2 > o\text{-NO}_2$

The absorption maxima and molar extinction co-efficients of some of the dyes reported in previous publication by one of us (A.K.S.) are collated in Table I for comparison.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzylidene (or nitrobenzylidene)-2-(5 or 6 or 7-iodo) 3oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene: On refluxing a mixture of benzaldehyde (or nitrobenzaldehydes) with equimolecular proportion of iodothioindoxyl in absolute ethanol and concentrated hydrochloric acid for about ten minutes, the dye separated out. The dyes were then recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. The m.p. of the compounds, crystalline shape, colour in H_2SO_4 (Conc.), dyeing shade on cotton from hydrosulphite vat and molecular formula and analysis are recorded in Tables II & III.

4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6 or 7-iodo) 3 oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthene: Equimolecular proportion of 6- or 7-iodothioindoxyl and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde were

dissolved in hot absolute ethanol. The mixture was heated together with strong hydrochloric acid. The dye precipitated out in yellow needles, which on washing with dilute ethanol gave a bright vermilion dye and were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE II

Compounds	Colour in Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Shade on cotton
M ₁	Green	Faint yellow
M ₂	Green	Light yellow
G ₁	Scarlet red	Very faint yellow
G ₂	Deep red	Very faint yellow
G ₃	Deep red	Very faint yellow
G ₄	Dark red	Orange red
G ₅	Scarlet red	Pink
G ₆	Scarlet red	Pink
L ₁	Scarlet red	Faint yellow
L ₂	Bluish violet	Very faint yellow
L ₃	Deep violet	Light yellow
L ₄	Greenish blue	Orange yellow
L ₅	Violet	Reddish violet
L ₆	Violet	Reddish violet

TABLE III

B = Benzaldehyde

D = Iodothioindoxyl

Com- pounds	Reactants	Appearance	Yield	M.P.	Formula	Analysis	
						%Found	%Required
M ₁	<i>o</i> -Nitro B (0.188 g.) +5-D (0.345 g.) +EtOH (10 ml.)	Yellow needles	0.27 g.	240-42°	C ₁₅ H ₈ NO ₃ SI	I, 30.95 S, 7.75	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
M ₂	<i>m</i> -Nitro B (0.188 g.) +5-D (0.345 g.) +EtOH (15 ml.)	Orange yellow needles	0.25 g.	212° (Shrink at 210°)	C ₁₅ H ₈ NO ₃ SI	I, 31.20 S, 7.91	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
G ₁	B (0.212 g.)+6-D(0.552 g) +EtOH (14 ml.)	Yellow (with brown tinge) needles	0.48 g.	157°	C ₁₅ H ₉ OSI	I, 34.95 S, 8.65	I, 34.89 S, 8.79
G ₂	<i>o</i> -Nitro B (0.259 g.)+ 6-D(0.473 g.)+EtOH (19 ml.)	Bright yellow needles (fibrous)	0.31 g.	200°	C ₁₅ H ₈ NO ₃ SI	I, 30.80 S, 8.02	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
G ₃	<i>m</i> -Nitro B (0.259 g.) 6-D(0.473 g.)+EtOH (18 ml.)	Yellow needles	0.55 g.	273-74°	C ₁₅ H ₈ NO ₃ SI	I, 31.28 S, 7.93	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
G ₄	<i>p</i> -Nitro B (0.302 g.) +6-D(0.552 g.)+EtOH (19 ml.)	Orange yellow needles	0.64 g.	259-60°	C ₁₅ H ₈ NO ₃ SI	I, 31.21 S, 7.94	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
G ₅	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino B (0.3 g.) +6-D (0.57 g.)+EtOH (15 ml.)	Red needles	0.55 g.	230-31°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ NOSI	I, 30.72 S, 7.93	I, 31.20 S, 7.86
G ₆	<i>p</i> -Diethylamino B(0.425 g.) +6-D (0.663 g.)+EtOH (15 ml.)	Deep red needles	0.7 g.	195-96°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ NOSI	I, 29.31 S, 7.62	I, 29.19 S, 7.35
L ₁	B(0.254 g.)+7-D (0.662g.) EtOH (15 ml.)	Bright yellow needles	0.55g.	171-72°	C ₁₅ H ₉ OSI	I, 34.61 S, 8.86	I, 34.89 S, 8.79

TABLE III (Contd.)

Com- pounds	Reactants	Appearance	Yield	M.P.	Formula	Analysis	
						%Found	%Required
L ₂	<i>o</i> -Nitro B(0.302 g.)+7-D (0.552 g.)+EtOH (17ml.)	Yellow needles (fibrous)	0.45 g.	211°	C ₁₅ H ₈ NO ₃ SI	I, 31.24 S, 8.13	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
L ₃	<i>m</i> -Nitro B(0.302 g.)+7-D (0.552 g.)+EtOH (17 ml.)	Yellow needles	0.58 g.	266-67°	C ₁₅ H ₈ NO ₃ SI	I, 30.92 S, 7.96	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
L ₄	<i>p</i> -Nitro B(0.302 g.)+7-D (0.552 g.)+EtOH (18 ml.)	Orange needles	0.56 g.	264-65°	C ₁₅ H ₈ NO ₃ SI	I, 31.12 S, 7.78	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
L ₅	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino B(0.298 g.) +7-D (0.552 g.)+EtOH (15 ml.)	Red needles	0.5 g.	199°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ NOSI	I, 31.43 S, 8.02	I, 31.20 S, 7.86
L ₆	<i>p</i> -Diethylamino B (0.354 g.) +7-D (0.552 g.)+EtOH (14 ml.)	Deep red needles	0.6 g.	131°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ NOSI	I, 29.13 S, 7.50	I, 29.19 S, 7.35

4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-or 7-iodo)3 oxy 2,3-dihydro-thionaphthenes: A solution of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde and the iodothioindoxyl in absolute ethanol was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid and was refluxed for about an hour, when the hydrochloride of the dye was obtained as a yellow needle. The solution was cooled to 45° and was filtered. The yellow product was washed with dilute ethanol and turned dark red. It was washed with ammonium hydroxide solution and hot water and then crystallised from absolute ethanol.

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